

USING MUSIC AND SOUND EFFECTS IN MUSEUMS

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In past decades, museums, art galleries, exhibition centres are interested to collaborate technology with their objects by using various audio-visual effects, textual decoration and lighting system. Commonly, the world is changing more rapidly rather than the population is adapting the modern one. One of the significant reason for this is becoming the emergence of technology, its fast developing, becoming the important part of humanity and daily life, also introducing in different spheres of society, especially in art and culture institutions, like museums and art galleries. The purpose of integrating so quickly is creating comfort and attraction to people.

One of the first step of organising this process was using background music and sound effects indoor spaces. The reason of starting from sounds can be that hearing is one of the five senses as well as the first which people start to feel before birth and it has the significant role in whole life. According the states of Lehmann, Sloboda, Woody(2007) " music in everyday life is generally used as 'background'. Recorded music will be playing, but the user will usually be doing something else, as well as listening the music."(p 232-3), it is understandable that background music or sound effects are not able to distract, annoy or lose the concentration.

Originally, music is a part of intangible cultural heritage, which are created from natural sounds and using musical instruments. The voices of nature is authentic and involved the of habitants, like animals, birds and humans, who live on the Earth or nature itself, sounds of water, wind, rain and others. These types of sound are usually used in Natural museums to give the second life for

collections, hence these effects are able to make alive the nature and animals in display, the result of this collaborating is more attractive and interesting. Additionally, they are unchanged through whole generations, that mean it connects all three generations (past, present, future), also the are easily associable and rememberable.

The instruments, which were used to compose musics, have a huge history as well as objects in museums. Additionally, Oakes in 2000, identified in his study choosing and associating the words in lyrics for instrumental music is possibly affect to individual responses to music. Moreover, musics are written in different periods and spaces that shows the elements of culture, life, history and art of that time, so all of these features make them unique, special and identical.

Subsequently, museums should use the classical music, the masterpiece of overtime that its history will be able to link with the period of composing, the message, feelings, which were shared by composers, masters of music, during those passed centuries. Integrating music with museum, increase the possibility of rebuilding the atmosphere of given time. Nina Simon in her posted Museum 2.0 Blog, while answering the question "Should museums play music in public spaces and in galleries?", reported that one of the advantages is becoming to create a certain atmosphere as well as to create the feeling of comfortable space.

The development of mass media in the twentieth century is influenced in creating modern versions of music with much more widely spreadness and availableness. Nowadays, modern music is created by using of technology rather than musical instruments that makes them more common and similar. Although modern music gives relaxation feelings, it doesn't have the deep history. But, historical or classical music shares the history, related emotions as well as motivates to study more.

Despite of replaying and recording the masterpiece many times by musicians, who added their own point of view, emotions, listeners are able to feel the

originality and authenticity of the meaning. Classical music are becoming far from daily life of young generation. For the reason that electronic music is influenced widely to society and classical type is becoming boring in the case of losing the meaning. Although, in the nineteenth century, live music could be heard only in private homes or a public concert hall. It shows that in past two centuries the value of live music dramatically changed.

The integrating are beneficial for both sites, music itself and museum. In order to educate, interest and sent to next future, it would be the great decision to use in displaying public institutions, like museums, art galleries, exhibition centres. The concept of these these type of places is offering a bridge between past, present and future. Moreover, these institutions make a chance to music for reborn its history, process of developing, original meaning and role in art and culture.

The experiment, done by University of Washington, 2016 in Renton History Museum, shows key findings, which were identified after interviewing the visitors, who were participated in the little House Exhibit under two conditions: music and no music. Firstly, music help to hold visitors longer in the exhibit. Also, participants found differences between the conditions. Secondly, it was clarified that music was positively influenced to learning more than usual.

Bruner(1990) demonstrated "music has long been considered an efficient and effective means for triggering moods and communicating nonverbally", that means the unique value of music as universal language. It can be problematic to explain the message and meaning of any display in museums for multilingual visitors, in this case it can be needable to find a solution with use of appropriate background music effects.

Jakubowski (2011) studied three different sounds(music, human, natural) in two levels(high,low) and their effects in museum exhibit. The research showed that " visitors in the classical music in low decibel condition remained in the

exhibit significantly longer than visitors in high and low decibel human voices conditions, natural low condition or classical high condition". Besides, it was underlined that correctly selected music sounds is exciting the positive emotions and visitor experience, the distinctive feature of this process is relating the topics of both ,music and exhibits,sides. In order to get high results and developments in Integrating music effects and museum objects, it should be accounted the place, topic, idea, period, and time of displaying.

References

Briana K. Brenner, University of Washington, a thesis submitted impartial fulfillment of requirements for the degree of Master of Arts.

Bruner, G. C. II. (1990). Music, Mood, and Marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(4), 94.

Jakubowski, R.D. (2011). Museum soundscapes and their impact on visitor outcomes (Doctoraldissertation). Retrieved from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Full Text. (Order No. 3454610)

Lehmann, A. C., Sloboda, J. A., & Woody, R. H. (2007). *Psychology for musicians: understanding and acquiring the skills*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Loureiro, S. M. C., Roschk, H. & Lima, F. (2019). The role of background music in the visitors' experience of art exhibition: music, memory, and art appraisal. *International Journal of Arts Management*. 22 (1), 4-24

Oakes, S. 2000. "The Influence of The Musicscape Within Service Environments." *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol. 14, no 7, p. 539-556.

Simon, N. (2011, June 14) Open thread: How do you feel about music museums?<http://museumtwo.blogspot.com/2011/06/open-thread-how-do-you-feel-about-music.html>.